

Transport of Indomethacin from carrageenan-gelatin nanogel

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This paper describes a single emulsion-solvent evaporation method to prepare biocompatible nanogel carriers by utilizing different concentrations of carrageenan and gelatin. The gels were characterized based on average particle size, zeta potential, SEM and release patterns. It was found that average particle size was in the range of 2000- 4000 nm after drug entrapment. An effort has been made to investigate release kinetics of Indomethacin (model drug) to study the transport from the nanogel carrier matrices. The entrapment efficiency was found to be nearly 40%. UV-visible spectrophotometric method was used for estimation of indomethacin content in the formulation. The prepared formulation exhibited 90% cumulative drug release for up to 24 hours.. The cytotoxicity study was performed for carrageenan & gelatin combinations on MCF7 breast cancer cell lines using MTT assay and the results suggest that the nanogel did not impart any significant level of toxicity. Therefore, the nanogel carriers could be exploited to entrap other therapeutic agents as well as growth factors. Overall, all the results prove the gels could be tuned to be a good candidate for biomedical applications.

Keywords: biopolymer, carrageenan, gelatin, nanogel, drug release